

Strategies for Holistic Social Development

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ABSTRACT: This paper aims to emphasize the significance of holistic social development for the contemporary society. A context in which understanding and dealing with such a complex subject requires that there are a number of areas that determine a holistic social development. These include: how technology is used, the integration of technology in the learning process, which leads to the development of students, the promotion of science and culture as factors generating personal, community and social development. These areas lead to developing ways in which people communicate with each other, both within the narrow school context, for example, as well as within the broader context of society, with implications for the relationship between individuals, their involvement in society and, implicitly, the design of strategies for holistic social development.
KEY WORDS: Holistic social development; sustainability; technology; students; science; culture; strategies

We are living in a growing society, in a broad process of development and adaptation, which inevitably implies a learning process. Thus, we also look at the holistic development of society by referring to strategies that help us achieve these goals. Therefore, we do not consider it, as some people might think, just an educational development, given that it is a learning process, but also an economic, financial and social one of an individual. We are talking about a holistic development, an integrated one combining several aspects and elements. We have several factors that together lead to specific strategies that need customized approaches.

Starting from the above-mentioned aspects, this research aims to emphasize the importance that the subject, the theme of holistic social development has for contemporary society. A context in which understanding and dealing with such a complex subject requires that there are a number of areas that determine a holistic social development. These include how technology is used, the integration of technology in the learning process, which leads to the development of students, the promotion of science and culture as factors generating personal, community and social development.

These areas lead to developing ways in which people communicate with each other, both within the narrow school context, for example, as well as within the broader context of society, with implications for the relationship between individuals, their involvement in society and, implicitly, the design of strategies for holistic social development.

Thus, a number of essential aspects are achieved, which play a crucial role in the holistic development of society, starting from the basic cell of the society that is the family, continuing through the educational institutions, whether we are talking about the gymnasium, high school or university level and reaching the community. In all these segments, a crucial role is played by science, culture and the development of communication. We come back to the aspect of communication that becomes a key element in the discussion of holistic social development strategies.

The mentioned aspects are highlighted in the everyday life of Romania through those Roma communities living on the poverty line who do not have access to social protection systems, specialized medical assistance or the possibility to follow a classical educational system.

It follows that a holistic development strategy of society must also take into account such situations, and such communities. As a consequence, their socio-economic situation constitutes a barrier to their social holistic development. It is necessary to design programs that aim at reducing social gaps and a holistic development at the community level.

The concept of holistic development is a relatively new one, which is why it is necessary to present some information about it.

We thus speak of an integral and integrated development of skills, knowledge, abilities, and values. This term of holistic development is understood as a complex but integrated development in terms of the person, the human being and the society. We come to the fact that the skills and knowledge necessary for sustainable development are acquired over the coming decades, so that people and society as a whole co-operate towards this holistic development of society. In this way, we have an integration, but also an interpenetration of several key elements that lead, as we have already mentioned, to sustainable development in the future as a society, to personal development if we refer to individuals or small groups. At country level, one of the purposes of this development is to ensure prosperity.

In order for this concept of holistic social development to work, we must understand the mechanisms that govern it. Thus, we talk about the specific capacities that children naturally accumulate in their first years of childhood. We are talking about a similarity to what has happened over time with ancient cultures and civilizations. Some of the most powerful were the Egyptian, Greek and Roman civilizations. At a careful analysis we observe a hierarchy of society that implies a common, unitary development, which also implies that the members of society have specific roles and duties. Involvement in society was also different. Some were learning as disciples, others were learning the meaning of philosophy, others were philosophers who were passing on the knowledge they had gained. What is interesting in this context is the model of Greece where we have the concept of democracy, a word that is made up of a *demos* that refers to the people and *kratos* that refers to power. By joining these two words, the meaning of democracy refers to the leadership of the people, to direct leadership directly exercised by the people in this case, a direct democracy because the people exercise their will directly. A similarity from this point of view is also found in the Church as an institution that can be compared to a certain extent with a society. We have people with different capacities and gifts, at different levels of knowledge, working together for development and achieving a common good.

When we refer to holistic concept as integrating the whole person, we mean integrating the environment and the emotional,

psychological, physiological, ethical and familial aspect. The above-mentioned aspects refer to both contemporary and person's history, which has happened over a longer time frame. But not only that, but when we talk about this concept of holistic development with application to the social development of a human being, we are considering its development in an integral person, one that integrates in its evolution capacities from a multitude of domains, of which we enunciate:

- (1) temperament, personality and self-views;
- (2) cognition;
- (3) emotions;
- (4) volition;
- (5) physical;
- (6) social/interpersonal;
- (7) moral character; and
- (8) citizenship.

These are all areas of great importance for a unitary, holistic development of a person in society. What is really interesting is that we are talking about a combination of areas from different spheres, namely from moral, religious, even physical, mental and social development such as citizenship. We have a progressive development that starts from the temperament, personality and the opinions of man, goes through the emotional and moral part, reaching the unitary development from a physical point of view, as well as the integration of the person thus formed into the society as a citizen. Citizenship is the element that shows man's dependence on society, interaction between the human sphere and the social sphere.

Evolution, the development of the human person does not happen at once, but it is a learning process that begins in childhood, continues in adolescence and reaches maturity with the man who better understands society, those around him. The success of this development requires a personalized and customized educational program for each individual situation. Although maturity does not ask what society does for you, but what you do for it, however, for a person to provide what is best, the society must have previously invested in its development from an educational point of view,

but also moral. We draw attention to the fact that today it tends more and more to a society without genuine values. We are talking about a relativism of moral ideas, of truths in a certain sphere of knowledge. Falseness is noticed in the fact that although stupidity is proclaimed emphatically, it tends to suppress only the fundamental truth revealed by the Bible. Although some people assert that the truth is universal, it does not take account of the same measure in the field of exact sciences. We are rhetorically asking why they are fighting only for a new man without self-conscience and faith in God, and do not apply the same measure in other areas of existence.

Belief in God should have its role in holistic social development just as education has. Thus, in order for today's young people to become tomorrow's trained people capable of supporting the holistic development of society, they need to invest in education. The same thing is also required for society, to support education in the conditions in which during the youth, people accumulate not only information, but also skills. To be able to thrive as adults, children and young people need a good environment to provide them with the appropriate learning experiences.

We have several models that show us the steps towards achieving the holistic social development process. A first step would be to identify those capacities that can be developed, some of which can be directed through a guided learning process. The follow-up step aims at conducting a inquiry on the research available to continue examining the contexts in which people as individuals will use their capabilities.

We have a holistic development of society, and within it we have a holistic development of youth, one that, although it also contemplates contemporary aspects, nevertheless does not depart from classical values. We do not want to create a new framework, but creating over the existing one that allows young people to acquire new knowledge, to thrive. We have an object, a long-term development that must be matched with values. If youth prosper only from the material point of view, it is only through the accumulation of perennial values and does not thrive spiritually by acquiring eternal values. That is why it is important in this article to move from assumptions to objectives. Through objectives in connection with the holistic development of youth, we have in mind both the human

and the social component. Within the human component we are considering a physical, psychological, but also a spiritual component. Thus we refer to the physical integrity of young people, to the fact that they are whole people recognized as such by the people around them. Moreover, we consider here not only a physical development, but also an educational one, as they acquire certain values through education. Education that correlates with the spiritual principles extracted from the Bible leads to ethical behavior and the person also shows psychological integrity. Taking into account the above-mentioned issues, it is necessary that the holistic development approaches of youth should have a specific form. That is why we need to have a holistic development strategy for both young people and society.

Holistic Development Strategies

Holistic social development needs a strategy because we have principles to be respected, services to be implemented and these cover various areas such as education, which we have already mentioned, personal development, therapeutic intervention, cultural aspects highlighted by different activities which can be related to entrepreneurial development. Although it is a new field, it is important in the strategy of holistic development of a society, as is sport and reintegration into society. Reasons for reintegration of a person into society can be multiple, but the process itself is quite important. Another aspect that we bring to the fore when speaking of holistic development is the spiritual one. There can't be a complex development without an anchoring of faith in the values stated in the Book of Books. Therefore, a number of services need to be developed to achieve the proposed objectives.

(1) Developmental in Nature

Developmental in nature refers to a normal development of a person from a physical, emotional and spiritual point of view. People should be helped to broaden their knowledge horizons, develop and grow by acquiring knowledge and developing skills. One of the procedures

by which this goal can be achieved is the accumulation of knowledge through education. We have a process that takes into account progressive learning through experience, learning from successes and failures. In this process, people, especially young people, must be supported and encouraged, they must be excited about what they are doing, have positive thinking and trust that they will be able to complete what they have started, what they intended to do.

(2) Restorative and Rehabilitative

The restoration and rehabilitation of a person implies an active involvement, but also a great deal of tactfulness in the successful accomplishment of this objective. We are talking about people who have been in conflict with state laws, have violated them, and for this they have been punished. Once the punishment has been reached, the persons in question must be reintegrated into society, and moreover they must acquire the correct values. The fact that they paid for their mistake does not mean they are rehabilitated. The stigma of condemnation, the suspicion and the need for them to prove that they have understood their mistake, have taken the consequences and want to be part of the society by accepting its rules remain.

Involvement can also be beneficial for society by the fact that these people are integrated they are no longer marginalized or no longer withdraw from society, from the attributions and responsibilities of a citizen to get involved again in illegal things. There are several ONGs involved in this sphere to support these people. The Church can and must also get involved. A truly new man, a changed person is just the one transformed by the Christian message. That's why some Christians are putting into practice, sometimes even at the risk of their lives, the command to love their neighbor.

(3) Effective Communication

Communication is an area that is increasingly important in contemporary society. Man has this important feature received

from the divinity to communicate. He communicates in the family, at school, at work, in society. That is why it is important for him to learn to communicate and at the same time to relate.

People have communicated in various ways since ancient times and we remain astonished today by the richness of the forms of communication. It is imperative that a person knows how to communicate their feelings, thoughts, opinions and at the same time be able to support them regardless of gender, ethnicity, race or level of education. It is worth mentioning that what we have outlined above are criteria and issues that often remain at the stage of desideratum because it is clear that, unless a person is natively equipped with very good communication ability, the level of education has a very important role in the communication process. On the other hand, communication is not a one-sided process, that is, only one person transmits information but is a complex system involving two or more people, one of which is a transmitter and the other or at least one of them is a receiver. Effective communication also involves the transmission of a clear message, which requires understanding of the message and ensuring that it is transmitted and received by the person or institution to which it is intended without suffering disturbance.

At the individual level, education is also considered, because it has the role of helping to form a way of understanding and analyzing information. It can happen that someone is communicating something and the receiver does not understand the message or decode it properly. When talking about communication, we mean both verbal and non-verbal communication, each of these two ways being important.

(4) Multi-Disciplinary Approach to Programs

From effective communication, a field that has a primarily personal applicability, we move to the multidisciplinary approach of programs. This type of approach, like the other ones we have referred to proves its importance when it comes to the holistic development of society. We are talking about a custom multidisciplinary approach on a case

by case basis. It is something similar to what is being attempted today in the pre-university education system, a student-centered education, but here we are referring to the child as an individual, as a member of society, we are considering a person who needs a social orientation. We are talking about a multidisciplinary approach that can take into account several stages, several areas to choose from. Starting from the main purpose of ensuring a complex, unitary, holistic development of the individual and society, we will develop programs to support those who need it.

We will seek to identify the opportunities that are appropriate for the counselor, but moreover, an interdisciplinary approach can be provided by offering spiritual help, choosing the educational, professional, and if necessary even psychological support.

We live today in a constantly changing world and the rapidity of these transformations and transitions from one system to another, from a set of values to another set of values or even non-moral and ethical value can bully the individual, and the ultimate goal of ensuring holistic development, as a whole of society, must be to provide support.

That is why a specialized and specific approach to programs, educational levels is recommended with the ultimate goal of meeting the individual, the citizen and the person by offering school or professional orientation programs.

People need to be offered alternatives, which also provide them with a higher degree of security. It is also a real help in holistic development as an individual and in the holistic development of society. That's why people need to be integrated into society at the micro or macro level, but also encouraged to express themselves. They have to become a group, without losing the individuality of any of those who organize themselves like this.

The focus of holistic development is on integration, interconnection, collaboration and not on marginalization, on offering viable and sustainable programs.

Another element to be remembered is the cultural one. Culture in turn is an element, but also a factor contributing to the objectives. In turn, communication integrates with education, sometimes it can even be confused, but also with technology or management. The

management term has long passed from the purely technical sphere and has even reached the class of students that can be organized taking into account a specific management.

Conclusion

The holistic development of society is a simple appearance, but in reality it covers a multitude of other areas and issues. We have gone through the integration of education, culture, management, and all this to provide a consistent organizational support to meet the needs of a society in the process of change. The ultimate goal is to build a holistic, durable and sustainable society that provides a child-friendly, youth-friendly development environment to provide them with options as well as security. Beyond all this, the most important aspect is that of eternal hope and security that can only be assured by one person, unique in His being, referring in this case to the Creator of the Universe.

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